

Minutes EB24-01
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
15 February 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

Apology

Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
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1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

SeqCode Prize (to be discussed as under the item Registry and Nomenclature Working Group)

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

Action items from previous meeting

1. KK to follow-up on the NSF's' RCN and ICB funding.

Waiting for feedback on a current proposal before submitting a new proposal.

2. FW and LMR to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

FW and LMR will meet to explore the possibilities.

3. FV to remind the SeqCode Community via email of the discussion of the proposal to amend the SeqCode, and the SeqCode prize. The help of volunteer nomenclature curators will also be requested.

Done, but no response yet for assistance with curation.

4. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

PH to provide feedback.

5. LMR and MC to look into the possible incorporation of GAN in the registry.

GAN could be incorporated. Program will assist with the creation of names and could reduce the workload of the curators. Could not be used as a check for names proposed by authors.

6. MC to prepare a proposal for a roundtable discussion at ISME19.

FW suggested a candidate for the community panel. Proposal to be submitted on 16 February.

7. Redacted

8. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.

BW to manage processes and submit final report to ISME Executive. IS, LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities by March 1.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

The public discussion of the Whitman et al. proposal to amend the SeqCode is completed and IS has provided the necessary documentation required for the ballot. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot via surveymonkey. Voting will be open for 1 month. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote. Results will be compiled and shared by FV and LMR.

Standards Working Group

No new issues to report.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 221 names have been validated and another 229 have been endorsed.

LMR expressed the concern that the current curation team is working at capacity. LMR hopes that Melandre van Lill could continue as part of the curation team to assist with the curation of names with Marike Palmer as mentor. Juan Valero (from the group of Maria Dzunkova, Universidad de Valencia) and Emily St John (from ALR lab) will join the team to assist with checking the genome quality requirements.

The activities of the SeqCode will be promoted at the IMMSA Webinar and the NMDC Champions program.

MC and LMR will investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.

The Neo-Latin department of the University of Innsbruck has expressed interest in joining a possible EU COST (European Cooperation in Science and Technology) action.

Three submissions were received for the SeqCode Prize. The entries will be shared with the EB and members who do not have an association with one or more of the applicants will evaluate the entries and make the final decision.

Reconciliation Commission

The discussion of the proposal for validation of a name linked to a poor-quality genome to ensure the stability of the names of the higher-ranking taxa has been completed and the documentation was shared with the SeqCode Community. There is now a 3-month period for objections to be raised. If no objections are received by 12 March 2024 the decision will be ratified.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

EB members will provide their comments for discussion at the next EB meeting. Comments should only focus on the proposed amendments to the ICNP and their implications. Individuals are welcome to provide comments on the proposal via the ICSP Slack channel.

6. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to list SeqCode presentations and share material linked to these presentations on the shared drive.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. BW to manage the compilation a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode and submit it to the ISME Executive. Publication in ISME Communications to be investigated.
3. IS, LMR, KK and MC to provide a short summary of their activities for the SeqCode report by 1 March 2023.
4. FV and LMR to liaise with the ISME office to prepare the ballot for the proposed changes to the SeqCode.
5. FV to alert the SeqCode Community of the opportunity to vote.
6. FV and LMR to compile the results of the ballot and share it with the EB.
7. MC and LMR to investigate the possibility of linking the SeqCode registry to relevant entries on NCBI.
8. FV to share the SeqCode prize entries with EB members to evaluate the entries and make the final decision.
9. EB members to provide their comments on the Arahall et al. proposal for discussion at the next EB meeting.
10. MC to contact a candidate for community panel proposed by FW and submit the roundtable proposal for ISME19.
11. All to reflect and suggest on more involvement of ISME with SeqCode.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. FW and LMR to look for Chinese funding opportunities.
3. PH to investigate the possibility of continued funding from ISME for work on the registry.

Minutes prepared by FV, 18 February 2024

Approved 27 February 2024